

INFORMATION REGARDING THE IMPORTANCE AND TECHNOLOGY OF CULTIVATION OF THE PLANT ECHINACEA PURPLE

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Abstract. *The given article presents information regarding the botanical description, geographic distribution, use in folk and modern medicine, as well as the technology of cultivation of *Exonium officinalis red (Echinacea purpurea (L.) Moench)*. The results of preliminary studies on the development of a scientific and practical basis for growing the medicinal plant *Exodonia red* are also obtained. During the experiments, the seeds of the *E. purpurea* plant were sown manually to a depth of 3-5 cm. Before planting, the seeds were treated with biofertilizers based on microorganisms. The seeds were planted in pots measuring 60x30 cm, 3-4 seeds were placed in each nest. It has been proven that while using organic and microbiological fertilizers, a large mass can be obtained from the above-ground parts of the plant, the stem, leaves and flowers and from the underground parts, the root stem and roots. Since the plant is perennial in its life form, in the first year only the underground (root) and above-ground (bunch of leaves) bodies were formed, then from the second year of vegetation it is generative (flowering, fruiting), it was decided to switch to the form.*

Keywords: *purple coneflower, medicinal, vegetative, generative, biofertilizer, spherical leaf, flower, fruit, traditional medicine, seeds, modern medicine, disease.*

INTRODUCTION

At present time the plants are widely used in all spheres of human economic activity, in particular, in medicine, folk medicine, industry. In recent years, the widespread development of science has made it possible to study the chemical composition of many plants, isolate various substances and study their physiological properties, as a result of which the number of new medicinal plants increases every year.

It is important to suggest that according to the resolution of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, dated May 20, 2022 N. PD-251 "On measures to organize the cultivation and processing of medicinal plants and their widespread use in treatment", growing and processing plants, supporting the creation of cultural plantations of medicinal plants, as well as drugs for the prevention and treatment of diseases, special attention is paid to the issues of widespread use of plants.

In this regard, the study of the introduction of natural flora and medicinal plants belonging to foreign flora, which are widely used in folk and official medicine, determining the amount of useful chemicals in plant organs, and studying their medicinal properties are of important scientific and practical importance. practical significance is one of the issues.

LITERATURE ANALYSIS

Definitely, the plant red echinacea occupies a special place due to the fact that it contains a large number of biologically active substances and preparations from it are widely used these days. The medicinal plant red echinacea has been cultivated in the world since 1692. This plant

was brought to Russia as an ornamental plant at the beginning of the 19th century [1], S. Khujaniyazova introduced red echinacea as an ornamental plant in Tashkent Botanical Garden in 1950, because of its beautiful flower, who studied the growth, development, biological and morphological features of the plant [2].

Besides that, red echinacea is used not only in folk, but also in scientific medicine, preparations made from its above-ground and underground parts are included in the state pharmacology of European countries, Russia, Belarus and Ukraine, which is considered as a medicinal plant rich in biologically active substances [3, 4]. In foreign and domestic publications, as well as in some scientific studies, there is information that the duration of the growing season of the valuable plant Echinacea is 6-7 months. According to M. U. Ollayorov (2009), the length of the plant seed is 0.42 cm, the width is 0.18 cm, the shape of the seed is in the form of a long cone, the upper part is covered with protective shells [6, 7].

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

It is not a secret that Echinacea rubra, Echinacea is a valuable perennial medicinal plant belonging to the Asteraceae family. There are 5 species of Echinacea on earth. All these plant species are erect perennial rhizomes. The height of these plants reaches 90-150 cm. The color of the seeds is usually gray-red or brown. In our country, the plant blooms from July to late autumn. Its seeds ripen in August and October. The vegetative and generative organs of this plant, which are used for medicinal purposes, are collected at the time of seed ripening.

Moreover, the leaves of the plant are large, usually the leaves at the root of the plant are wide lanceolate and attached to the stem by a long leaf bandage. The tip of the leaf blades in the upper part of the stem is narrowed and pointed. The flowers of the plant are large basket-shaped inflorescences 2-3 cm long and 10-15 cm in diameter. The basket of purple coneflower is multi-flowered, usually called a "capitate inflorescence" or "flower head". The petals are purple-pink or red-brown, up to 5 cm long. The red coneflower plant reproduces vegetatively and generatively.

However, this plant is found in almost all European countries. It is also widespread in India, Japan, Australia, America, Russia, Ukraine and the North Caucasus. Naturally, it usually grows on sandy river banks, as well as in dry or moist soil conditions.

It is worth mentioning that other species of the genus Echinacea are found in nature in North America and Mexico (especially red coneflower in the subtropical zones of North America). All species of the Echinacea family are perennial mesophotic plants.

Additionally, in the first year of vegetation, this plant produces a bunch of 7-13 leaves. From the third year of life of the plant, the number of spherical leaves reaches 30-40 and it enters the generative period. In the third year of vegetation, the plant is in the middle-aged generative period. This plant is predominantly light-loving and can grow quite well in open and semi-shaded places. There are opportunities for growing the red echinacea plant and its effective use in various soil and climatic conditions of our country. Purple echinacea has been used since ancient times in folk and modern medicine to treat various diseases. Red echinacea is widely used, especially in American and European folk medicine. Echinacea preparations are widely used to improve the body's immune system, to treat metabolic disorders, especially diabetes and liver diseases. It is also used to eliminate and treat poisoning caused by food products and various drugs.

It is known that purple coneflower is not only an ornamental plant, but also of great importance in the pharmaceutical and perfume industries. It has long been used in folk medicine in American and European countries. Due to its complex medicinal properties, red coneflower is

widely known as the "queen of medicinal plants". Until then, red coneflower was widespread as an ornamental plant due to its beautiful flowers, but now it is included in the ranks of valuable medicinal plants, and foreign pharmaceutical companies have begun to produce various drugs from its above-ground and underground parts. industrial enterprises have been closed [7].

The pharmacological properties of purple coneflower preparations allow them to be widely used in the prevention of different diseases, especially, during the onset of colds, in the treatment of various infectious diseases, as well as in improving the health of patients affected by radiation. Medicines are mainly prepared from echinacea raw materials in the pharmaceutical industry. In modern medicine, above-ground and underground organs are used. It is distinguished by the presence of many substances, such as essential oil, echinococci glycoside, resins, betaine, phenolic acids.

What is more important, purple coneflower blooms from the second half of summer until autumn. Echinacea flowers are red, white, pink, orange and yellow.

While creating industrial plantations of purple coneflower, given its bioecological features, it is advisable to choose open areas. Red coneflower is a light-loving plant. However, it can also grow well in semi-shaded areas. According to its importance, we can set the task of growing this valuable medicinal plant in different soil and climatic conditions of Fergana Valley, based on organic farming and assessing changes in its chemical composition.

Purple coneflower seeds are usually sown manually to a depth of 3-5 cm. Before sowing, it is advisable to treat the seeds with biofertilizers, based on microorganisms. The seeds are sown in trays measuring 60x30 cm. Three to four seeds are placed in each nest. While using organic and microbiological fertilizers, a large mass can be obtained from the above-ground parts of the plant stems, leaves and flowers, and from the underground parts rhizomes and roots.

Since the plant is perennial in its life form, only underground (root) and aboveground (leaf bundle) organs were formed in the first year. During the observation period in the first year of vegetation, the plants formed up to 7-13 leaf balls. During the first year of vegetation, it was weeded and mowed 2-3 times a month, watered after each mowing. During the flowering period, it was additionally fed with microbiological fertilizers.

As we have already mentioned above, the generative phase of red echinacea begins mainly in the second year of vegetation. In the second year of growth and development of echinacea in the studied areas, generative stems appeared in the first days of May from shoots that appeared in the first days of April.

From the first ten days of May, it was determined that the polishing stage will begin, which will last until the mid-June. The flowering period also coincides with the first days of May. Full flowering of plants was observed from the end of June to the beginning of July until mid-August, the duration of flowering was 65-70 days.

Definitely, its seeds ripen from the first ten days of August to mid-October. In the third year of vegetation, the plant develops very well, the mass of the above-ground part and underground organs increases compared to the second year of vegetation.

In the third year of life, the vegetation of plants begins in early March. Before each watering, the sowing area was lightly mown, cleared of weeds, partially fed with microbiological fertilizers. The use of such agrotechnical measures ensures better development of the red echinacea plant and the accumulation of greater Phyto mass.

It should be mentioned that three times during the growth and development of the plant: the first one is in May, during the flowering period, the second one is in June, during the budding period; the third feeding was fed with microbiological fertilizers during the budding and ripening of fruits. Seeds can be planted in late autumn and early spring, with 7-8 kg of seeds required per hectare.

CONCLUSION

By summarizing it should be suggested that at the time of a plant is propagated by seeds, in the first year of vegetation only the root ball produces leaves, which is in a dormant period. The flowering period of the plant begins in the second year of vegetation. Starting from the second year of vegetation, medicinal raw materials can be harvested from the above-ground parts of the plant.

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